

ABOUT IMPROVING THE MECHANISM OF WORK WITH LOW-ABSORBING
READERS BASED ON THE TEXT AND ASSIGNMENTS STUDIED IN
INTERNATIONAL ASSESSMENT PROGRAMS

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Abstract. This article focuses on improving assignments used in conducting PISA international assessment program research and providing effective support to institutions and students participating in the program on work on assignment texts.

Keyword: PISA international assessment, reading literacy, assignments, text, reader.

ОБ СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИИ МЕХАНИЗМА РАБОТЫ С
МАЛОПОНИМАЕМЫМИ ЧИТАТЕЛЯМИ НА ОСНОВЕ ТЕКСТА И ЗАДАНИЙ,
ИЗУЧЕННЫХ В ПРОГРАММАХ МЕЖДУНАРОДНОЙ ОЦЕНКИ

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена совершенствованию заданий, используемых при проведении исследований международной программы оценивания PISA, и оказанию эффективной поддержки учреждениям и студентам, участвующим в программе, по работе над текстами заданий.

Ключевые слова: международная оценка PISA, читательская грамотность, задания, текст, читатель.

The fact that in recent years, as a result of the reforms carried out in our country, the indicators of tremendous economic growth are achieved further increases the demand for qualified personnel and mature specialists in all areas. It is in itself that the education of students increases all-round attention. In a time when our country is rapidly developing on the path of innovative development, it is necessary to comprehensively support the creative ideas and creativity of the future young people, to form their knowledge, skills and qualifications, to improve the assessment system based on advanced foreign experiences, international criteria and requirements, to study international experiences along the way, to conduct a comprehensive comparative analysis of, it is important to work closely with research institutions. To this end, by the decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan “on measures to organize international research in the field of assessment of the quality of education in the public education system” dated December 8, 2018, No. 997, the National Center for the implementation of international research on the assessment of the quality of Education under the state inspection At the same time, the tasks of participation in international research on the assessment of the quality of education were established:

PIRLS-assessment of the level of reading and understanding of the text of Elementary 4th graders;

TIMSS-assessment of literacy of 4th and 8th grade students in natural-scientific subjects;

TALIS-study of the environment of training and education and the working conditions of teachers in general secondary educational institutions of the leader and pedagogical personnel;

PISA is an assessment of the literacy rate of 15-year-old students in reading, mathematics and Natural Sciences.

EGRA and EGMA, on the other hand, give grades in elementary school reading and math skills. According to the results of the assessment, new training programs, teaching methods and approaches will be adapted for the good performance of the youth of Uzbekistan. Of particular importance in this place are the texts to be obtained for assignments in international assessment programs.

Large volumes of texts are organized from the beginning of several lines and separated into larger parts, such as sections, chapters and books. Small-scale texts, on the other hand, can be tabular in form, composed of several tables. These two texts are classified into types such as static or active. Mixed and complex format texts, on the other hand, are static in most cases in the form of active text. Static-looking texts depict images and graphs, which are an integral part of them. In active texts, videos, animations and audio files can be found, which is an integral part of them. The use of video and animation in current evaluation programs is limited to some extent, due to the fact that they require additional conditions, while audio materials are not used at all.

Currently, large-scale texts are widely used on the program scale. Examples of large-scale texts include newspaper news, essays, works, short stories, and letters. In large-scale texts, the structure of the text content is indicated using the title and content so that it is understandable to readers. The text also displays introductory words that represent sequence (order) (“first”, “second”, “third”, and so on), “therefore,” cause-and-effect relations between pieces of text such as “hence”, and a number of similar cues (e.g., from the sentence-end punctuation clause).

PISA studies suggest that the complexity of assignments in reading literacy is not an obstacle to student learning, but a necessary resource for them to generate competencies and skills in problem solving.

In recent years, there has been debate over whether assessment of students' reading-comprehension skills based on memory, answering text-based questions after their introduction to the text, is more effective than tests conducted in direct research. It is clear that working with the text you met a long time ago and responding will create difficulties for students, this aspect of Reading Literacy in the program was also taken into account. It was also found that if the reader was given a text assignment and the text was withdrawn after a short period of time, the reader's reading and comprehension skill would be confused with the memory retention skill. In fact, the read-and-understand skill is closely related to the memory retention skill, and the two cannot be learned separately from one another. With this in mind, the changes currently made regarding the PISA reading literacy assessment procedure have not justified themselves. In order to study this issue, it is envisaged that the time spent on reading the text given in the subsequent abstracts of PISA studies, the time allotted for repeating the text when answering questions and the total time set for completing the task will be taken into account.

Based on the purpose and internal structure of the text, its type is determined. Main text types:

- illustrative texts;
- narrative texts;
- expressive texts;

Descriptive texts contain information about the nature of objects in space. What are such texts usually? there will be an answer to the interrogation. There are different forms of descriptive texts. Impressionistic descriptive texts are composed of subjective representations of directions,

qualities, and relationships in space, while technical descriptive texts include spatial objective observations. Technical descriptive texts use formats such as diagrams and images.

Narrative texts refer to the characteristics of Jims despite the fact that the information is at no time. When are narrative texts usually?, in what sequence? and why? questions will be explained on the basis, they will also have different forms. Narrative texts define actions and events as being approached from a subjective side. Story-based material invites readers to independently reflect on what is happening or is happening. Narrative texts include works, short stories, plays, biographers, comic books, and events.

Expressive texts provide information on which complex or mental concepts can be analyzed. In this text, it is illuminated how elements enter into a relationship with each other and form a whole or cohesion in content, and how? responds to interrogation. Expressive texts have their own forms, in which mental concepts and experiences require interpretation from a subjective point of view. In expressive text, it is said how a concept is related to a word or term. To do this, the structure of the concept is understood in separate parts, and the relations in parts are obtained as a whole or integrity, which is analyzed separately. Examples of the type of expressive text include scientific articles, some diagrams, graphs, maps and entries.

The characteristic texts that prove indicate a connection between concepts or hypotheses. What are the characteristic texts that prove for? there will be an answer to the interrogation. Characteristic types of proof include the feedback the speaker expresses and the texts that motivate him to show his worldview and think. To the footnotes of the provable characteristic text are attached such concepts as phenomena, bodies and concepts that make up a separate system of feedback, dignity and trust. From the scientific side, proof texts state that hypotheses that are true or false are a phenomenon of knowledge and thinking, composed of objects and ideas.

Agreement characteristic texts are those aimed at achieving a goal, such as organizing meetings or meetings, asking for what needs to be done. Agreement characteristic texts are usually personal in nature, which explains why they are not included in any other type of text, allowing us to understand. Texts on agreement are usually based on agreements in personal knowledge and understanding. An example of these visual texts would be daily electronic correspondence, asking for something, or creating text messages for the purpose of planning.

Narrative texts express human perceptions, opinions about the universe, based on facts or documents, and have an important place in most national and international assessment programs. In texts given in other programs, textures and fantastic imagery, an artistic view of the world, represent imaginative concepts. In other studies aimed at assessing student reading literacy (e.g. the National Assessment of achievement in Education Program (NAEP), the International Assessment of achievement in education in Reading Literacy Research, and the International Program for assessing the level of reading comprehension of Primary students (PIRLS)), it aimed to study classifications of texts such as tissue, artistic and documentary texts. The differentiation between programs has become uncertain due to the authors ' use of fact-based texts in writing fiction as well.

The international program for assessing reading literacy of students of PISA also uses texts and artistic texts that are not of one type or another based on specific facts. As such, PISA does not aim to assess the difference between students ' knowledge of fact-based and artistic texts in their research. In PISA studies, textual and artistic texts are classified as narrative texts.

Characteristic texts, instructive and agreement texts do not have the ability to classify real-life texts with a characteristic of different types of text. A section of a textbook can be constructed from certain definitions (expressions), instructions aimed at solving the problem (demonstrative), a summary of finding a solution (narrative), and an image (descriptive) of certain bodies associated with the solution.

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